

Short Communication

A study on the relationship of Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of Secondary School Student of Papumpare District (A.P.)

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Abstract: The present study was carried out in Papumpare district of Arunachal Pradesh with an objective to examine the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition. The secondary level of education includes children between the age group of 14-18 years, the study was delimited to the sample of 2000 student of Class IX studying in Secondary schools in Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh. The result of the study suggests that there is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition. The present study was also conducted to find out the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment by taking into consideration of student's emotional intelligence and adjustment score categorised as high, average and below average. The result reveals that there is significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition under High category. There is significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition under Average category. There is no significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition under Below Average category.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Adjustment, Secondary School Student, Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh.

I. Introduction

As we venture into the dawn of the new millennium, adolescent development has emerged as a major area of psychological research. Adolescent have long been regarded as a group of people who are searching for themselves to find some form of identity and meaning in their lives (Erickson, 1968). They have also been regarded as a unique group with a wide range of difficulties and problems in their transition to adulthood.

One aspect of adolescents is their emotion, and within schools and society as a whole, this aspect has often been overlooked. Students are measured in terms of their performance and grades. They are assessed on how well they can play, act, draw, sing, and so forth. However, an intrinsic aspect of adolescence as well as all of us, and one that is usually not assessed, is what has been defined as emotional intelligence. Mayer and Salovey (1993), define emotional intelligence as, "A type of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others emotion, to discriminate among them, and to use the information to guide one's thinking and actions" (p.433). Emotional Intelligence is now considered by many as being essential for successful living (Goleman, 1995). Teaching adolescents about their emotion and how they deal with others as well as their own actions can be very helpful in their daily struggles. Furthermore, in order to encourage a

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smooth transition from adolescence to adulthood, a good understanding of emotion for adolescents is important in determining their psychological wellbeing. Emotion plays a very important role in our lives. It is essential to know how they affect our personal and social adjustment.

Adjustment refers to the ability of an individual to fit into his environment. Adjustment is an important factor to complete a person's goal successfully. It is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its need and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs. The dictionary meaning of the word 'adjustment' is, to make suitable, adapt, arrange, modify, harmonize or make correspondent. Adjustment, in psychology, the behavioural process by which humans maintain an equilibrium among their various needs or between their need and the obstacles of their environment. Gates, A.S. and Jersild, A.T. (1970) in their book "Educational Psychology" have defined adjustment is a continuous process by which a person varies his behaviour to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself and his environment."

II. Review of Related Literature:

Nicola S Schutte, et al (2002) conducted a study on "Characteristic emotional intelligence and emotional wellbeing" found that a course with a focus on emotion and the application of emotional skills gives first-year students resources that may be helpful in coping with academic and social adjustment challenges. Their findings indicated greater retention rates for students who participated in a freshmen transition course focused on emotions that students who did not receive such a course.

FarnShing Chen, Ying Ming Lin and Chia An Tu (2006) conducted a study on "**A study of the emotional intelligence and life adjustment of senior high school students**". The study was based on a random cluster sampling of senior high school students in Taiwan and Anhui province in mainland China. Significant difference was found between those students in Taiwan and Anhui province in China concerning emotional intelligence and life adjustment.

Hetal T. Patel (2006) in her study on "**A Study of Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of 9th Standard Student**" in context to their gender and area, comprises of 345 boys and 247 girls selected by stratified random sampling. One objective of the study was to establish the level of EQ and Adjustment of the students. The finding of the result shows there is a relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment and we should make some special efforts to develop emotional intelligence and adjustment of our students.

Another study in the field of emotional intelligence and adjustment can be seen by the study made by **Lennart Sjoberg (2008)** in his work on "**Emotional Intelligence and Life Adjustment**". The study was conducted on 153 respondents of Norway who were roughly representative of the population, including measurement of emotional intelligence, life/work balance and other indices of adjustment and social/psychological skills, and salary. The present study results support, in most respects, the EI construct, and

its postulated relation to successful life adjustment. High EI was associated with a better balance of life and work higher salary (especially for college-educated respondents). It was further noted that high EI was associated with better handling of failure and frustration, more creativity, less psycho phobia and higher self-esteem. Low EI was associated with loneliness.

Another study was carried out by **Shakuntalan Punia and Santosh Sangwan (2010)** in Hisar district of Haryana on the topic “**Emotional Intelligence and Social Adaptation of School Children**”. The objective of the study was to find out the emotional intelligence level of school children and its relation with their adjustment. A total of 120 children falling in the age group of 16 to 18 years, 60 each from randomly selected school of urban and rural areas were selected for the study. The finding of the study shows that majority of the respondents had normal to high level of emotional intelligence and average to excellent adjustment. Rural respondents were slightly better in their emotional intelligence, whereas, urban respondents were better adjusted against their counterparts. The emotional intelligence had significant positive relationship with adjustment of children. Caste, income and father’s occupation were main contributing factors in deciding the emotional intelligence and adjustment of respondents.

III. Objective of the Study

1. To examine the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition.

IV. Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition.

V. Methodology:

In this present study the researcher used proportionate stratified sampling technique. In case of proportionate stratified random sampling the units in each stratum are selected in the same proportion in which the strata stand in the total population. Selection of appropriate sample can go a long way in making the research study unique valid and reliable. The sample for the present study consisted of 2000 secondary school student out of which 1000 boys student and 1000 girls student studying in various secondary schools of Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh.

VI. Tools Used in the Study

For any research study, the researcher has to collect data and on the basis of that data conclusion has to be drawn and give some generalizations. These generalizations and conclusion will be correct and valid if the data

are methodically collected. For collecting reliable and valid data one needs reliable and valid tools for collections. The tools used for collecting data in the present study are.

- Emotional intelligence test developed by Ekta Sharma in 2011-09-05 for the age group 12 to 19 yrs.
- Adjustment Inventory for school students developed by A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh for the age group 14 to 18 yrs

VII. Statistical Techniques

The data were analysed using Pearson's coefficient of correlation method.

VIII. Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of Secondary School Student: To examine the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition, Pearson's coefficient of correlation method was employed and the values are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Coefficient of correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students.

Variables involved	N	Computed correlation value	Table value of 'r'	Significant level
Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment	2000	0.314	0.062	At 0.05 level

Table 1 shows that, computed 'r' value for Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school student in transition is 0.314, which is greater than table value of 'r' 0.062 is significant at 0.05 level, which indicates that, there is significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition.

The relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition has been examined further by taking into consideration of student's emotional intelligence and adjustment score categorised as high, average and below average.

Table 1.1

Coefficient of correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students categorised as High Emotional Intelligence.

Variables involved	N	Computed correlation value	Table value of 'r'	Significant level
Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment	92	0.163	0.138	At 0.05 level

Table 1.1 shows that, computed 'r' value for Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school student in transition under High category is 0.163, which is greater than table value of 'r' 0.138 is significant at 0.05 level, which indicates that, there is significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition under High category.

Table 1.2

Coefficient of correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students categorised as Average Emotional Intelligence.

Variables involved	N	Computed correlation value	Table value of 'r'	Significant level
Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment	1764	0.373	0.062	At 0.05 level

Table 1.2 shows that, computed 'r' value for Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school student in transition under Average category is 0.373, which is greater than table value of 'r' 0.062 is significant at 0.05 level, which indicates that, there is significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition under Average category.

Table 1.3

Coefficient of correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students categorised as Below Average Emotional Intelligence.

Variables involved	N	Computed correlation value	Table value of 'r'	Significant level
Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment	144	-0.28 (.30)	0.159	At 0.05 level

Table 1.3 shows that, computed 'r' value for Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school student in transition under Below Average category is -0,28, which is lower than table value of 'r' 0.159 is not significant at 0.05 level, which indicates that, there is no significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of secondary school students in transition under Below Average category.

IX. Conclusion and Suggestion

Emotion plays a very important role in our lives. It is essential to know how they affect our personal and social adjustments. Adjustment is an important factor to complete a person's goal successfully. It is the process by which a living organism maintain a balance between its need and the circumstances that influence the

satisfaction to these needs. The present study shows that there is significant difference in the emotional intelligence and adjustment of secondary school student. To ensure an improvement in Emotional Intelligence at school a holistic evaluation of the environment of the students should be done. The following are some of the recommendations:

1. According to the result of this study, student's emotional intelligence and adjustment are related. School administration could put emotional intelligence lessons into the curricula of school education.
2. Conduct a student consulting programme to reinforce student's abilities for emotional understanding and control.
3. Provide class activities such as outdoor education, Parents' Day, etc. to facilitate consultations with parents and establish positive communication between the teacher and students.
4. Increase the interaction between fellow students and reinforce communication abilities to improve relationships.
5. Teachers should facilitate students' self-emotion control, classroom management and emotional consulting abilities to reduce the adverse effects of students' emotional disorders and bad adaptation.
6. To cultivate the students' improved emotional management, teachers require to update their own emotional control abilities. For this teacher should be encouraged to participate in education consultation, career training and related professional knowledge to achieve higher educational effectiveness.

Facilitating a positive family environment is important to augment life adjustment abilities which can be done by increasing interaction between parents and children, families can be engage in the school's parenting activities to heighten children's emotional intelligence and promote the ability to recognise and control personal emotions.

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